

Relationship of Emotional Quotient and Academic Performance on the Criminology Licensure Examination

Radam, Judith A., Litawan, Stephanie A., Sanchez, Krixzyne Mae M., Rito, Janeil, Lamsis, Rhoald Duane S., Mania, Edwin Edilberto N., RGC, EdD

Abstract

Passing the Criminology Licensure Examination is a major goal for future law enforcement professionals in the Philippines. This study looked at how academic performance and emotional quotient (EQ) are connected, and how both affect students' success in the exam. Academic performance is based on grades and performance in criminology subjects, showing how well students are prepared mentally. EQ includes self-awareness, emotional control, empathy, and social skills—qualities that are important in the stressful field of law enforcement. Using a quantitative-correlational method, the study gathered data from criminology graduates by reviewing their grades and EQ test results. The findings show a moderate to strong link between high EQ and better exam scores. This suggests that strong thinking skills alone were not enough. Students with both good grades and high EQ handled stress better, stayed resilient, and performed well on the test. The study highlights the need for a well-rounded education in criminology. It recommends adding emotional quotient training to the curriculum so students can develop both academic knowledge and emotional skills. This approach can help future criminologists succeed in the exam and thrive in their careers in the criminal justice system

Keywords: *criminal justice, curriculum, knowledge, law enforcement, self-awareness*

Introduction

Criminology education was no exception, with shifts to remote learning, alterations in practical training, and potential psychological stressors affecting students' academic engagement and preparedness. As the world transitions into a post-pandemic era, it is crucial to understand the long-term effects of these disruptions on the academic performance and professional readiness of Criminology graduates.

This study focused specifically on post-pandemic board exam takers, defined as those who completed their Criminology education and took the licensure examination after the major disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. While previous research may have explored the immediate impacts of the pandemic on education, there was a noticeable gap in establishing a baseline understanding of the academic performance of these "products of the pandemic" in the high-stakes context of the Criminologist Licensure Examination.

The variables of this research study are emotional quotient, academic performance, and the Criminology Licensure Examination, which were used in the primary objective of the study, which is to explore the complex relationships that exist between a student's academic standing and their ability to pass the licensure exam. Graduates in the BS Criminology program of Saint Mary's University of the Criminal Justice Education Department are expected to be globally competitive. The individual student grades in their major and minor topics, the OJT grades, and the pre-board grades of Batches 2022–2024 were the main subjects of the study's investigation.

The study explored and analyzed the influence of students' academic profiles on the Criminology Licensure Examination. The central focus of this study is to analyze the impact of students' emotional quotient and academic performance. The outcomes of this research can guide the development of Criminology curricula that strategically incorporate support for students with

lower emotional quotient, potentially through initiatives facilitated by the Guidance and Testing Office (GTO). Moreover, this study was to provide a basis for the GTO of Saint Mary's University to refine its services to better assist students, especially those seeking to improve their emotional quotient and self-confidence. By examining how students' profile variables affect their preparedness and motivation for the licensure exam, this research offers significant benefits for students, reviewers, instructors, relevant organizations, and future academic inquiries.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to explore and analyze the relationship between students' academic profiles and the Criminology Licensure Examination results from 2022 to 2024. This research is crucial for understanding how the profile variables of the respondents may impact students' confidence and motivation as they take the criminology licensure exam. The study was conducted from August to December 2024.

This study determines the profile of respondents, which includes emotional quotient and academic performance. Additionally, the licensure exam performance of criminology students. Furthermore, there is no significant relationship between the profile variables and the Criminology Licensure Examination. Finally, a dissemination of a comprehensive information campaign was conducted, this campaign aimed to highlight the significance of emotional quotient in academic settings and was tailored for key stakeholders, including Dr. Felipe V. Nantes Jr., the Dean of School of Teachers Education and Humanities, Mrs. Jeanette D. Manuel, the Department Head of Criminal Justice Education, and Mr. Samuel B. Damayon, the Dean of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS).

Methodology

This chapter discusses the methods that the researchers used in conducting the study, which had the following sections: Research Design, Research Locale, Research Tool, Data Gathering Procedure, Treatment of Data, and Ethical Considerations.

The study used a descriptive-correlational method to explore the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The descriptive part was used for the profile of respondents in terms of emotional quotient and academic performance, while the correlational part was used to determine any significant relationship between the emotional quotient and academic performance, and the criminology licensure examination. The findings from both descriptive and correlational parts were used as the basis for the recommendations.

This study was conducted at Saint Mary's University (SMU). This university is in Bayombong in the Province of Nueva Vizcaya, Region 02 in the North Central part of Luzon. It is one of the private higher education institutions in the province. The study's participants were this institution's Bachelor of Science in Criminology graduates who had passed the Criminologists' Licensure Examination (CLE) from the year 2022 to 2024. SMU was ranked 10th by LocalPulse.net in the 2019 Best Philippine Schools to Study Criminology.

The archival method was used because the necessary information was already given, wherein the researchers received the coded information. The target of this study, based on the PRC website, was the board passers from June 2022, December 2022, April 2023, August 2023, February 2024, July 2024, and August 2024. This study focused on post-pandemic board exam takers or products of the pandemic. The information was gathered from the registrar. Specifically, we sent a letter requesting access to the registrar's file, including the grades of those who passed the 2022 to 2024 CLE. Only the grades of those who passed were requested, and no other registrar files were gathered. The Guidance and Testing Office (GTO) determined their emotional quotient; the dean evaluated

their academic performance, and the PRC administered the CLE. As a kind of purposive sampling technique, total population sampling involves the researcher's decision to look at the entire population with a certain set of characteristics.

To gather the list of passers of the CLE from 2022 to 2024, the researchers first prepared a consent letter addressed to the Dean of the School of Teacher Education and Humanities (STEH). This formal request aimed to obtain the PRC results of the CLE, along with their Emotional Quotient (EQ) from the GTO and General Weighted Average (GWA) from the Registrar's Office. The letter was also forwarded to the Vice President of Administration (VPA) and the researchers' thesis adviser. Upon approval, the researchers commenced the data-gathering phase. After collecting the data, they began to analyze the information gathered about the graduates using the theory of this research. To ensure confidentiality, the researchers were not allowed direct access to personal records; instead, the Dean of STEH encoded the data to anonymize the identities of the participants. All information gathered was stored in a secured and accessible database, available only to the thesis adviser and designated faculty members. The entire process was strictly monitored and overseen by the researchers' thesis adviser to maintain data privacy and integrity throughout the study.

This research utilized the Frequency Count, Weighted Mean, and Standard Deviation. These were used to analyze the emotional quotient and academic performance of the CLE passers. The following range of mean values was used to describe the collected data gathered from the institution (Badua, 2020).

Results and Discussion

Section 1. Profile of Respondents in Terms of Emotional Quotient and Academic Performance

Table 4

Emotional Quotient Profile of the Respondents

BarOn EQ Factors	Mean	SD	QD
Intrapersonal	84.35	8.33	Low
Interpersonal	79.17	14.98	Very low
Stress Management	86.83	12.94	Low
Adaptability	89.48	16.10	Low
General Mood	82.83	13.52	Low
Overall Level of Emotional	79.78	12.38	Very low

Legend: under 70(Markedly Low), 70-79(Very low), 80-89(Low), 90-109(Average), 110-119(High), 120-129(Very High), 130+(Markedly High)

The BarOn Emotional Quotient (EQ) assessment reveals varying levels of emotional intelligence across different factors. The Intrapersonal factor (M=84.35, s=8.33) will have a description of "low", Interpersonal (M=79.17, s=14.98) and Overall Emotional Functioning (M=79.78, s=12.38) are "very low" scores are classified as, indicating potential areas for personal growth. In contrast, Stress Management (M=86.83, s=12.94), Adaptability (M=89.48, s=16.10), and General Mood (M=82.83, s=13.52) are considered "low", suggesting strengths in managing pressure and adjusting to change. Overall, while they demonstrated solid adaptability and stress resilience, development in emotional awareness, interpersonal skills, and mood regulation would enhance their emotional intelligence profile. The findings suggest a critical varied in emotional quotient among the respondents. While individual domains such as stress management and adaptability show high potential, the overall level of emotional intelligence reveals a difference between self-perception and

actual emotional quotient. The particularly low score in Interpersonal skills signals a need for intervention in communication, empathy, and relationship-building areas. Students may struggle with collaboration, conflict resolution, and effective social interaction. The high Positive Impression score might reflect an attempt to mask emotional challenges rather than address them. Programs aiming to enhance authentic emotional regulation, not just outward positivity, should be prioritized in educational settings.

Numerous studies have shown a moderate but consistent positive correlation between emotional quotient and academic performance. For example, a meta-analysis by Sánchez-Álvarez et al. (2020) found a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and student achievement, especially among adolescents. Similarly, MacCann et al. (2020) concluded that ability-based EQ measures were better predictors of academic success compared to self-report measures. These findings indicate that students who can effectively regulate emotions, adapt to stress, and maintain a positive mood are more likely to perform better academically.

The profile reveals that while students appear capable of managing emotions on a surface level, they lack deeper interpersonal connections and consistent emotional application. Schools must focus on holistic EQ development beyond a positive impression to cultivate emotionally healthy, socially competent individuals. Strengthening EQ among students, especially those in the low to moderate performance bracket, may contribute significantly to better academic outcomes and reduced emotional distress. This supports the inclusion of EQ training as part of educational interventions aimed at improving both emotional well-being and academic success.

Table 5

Academic Performance Profile of the Respondents

Academic Performance	F (n=23)	%	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Very Good	6	26.09			
Passing	13	56.52	88.27	2.88	Passing
Good	4	13.39			

Legend: 74 and below (Failed), 75-80(Passing), 81-83(Good), 84-89(Very Good), 90-95(Excellent) and 96-100(Distinguished)

Table 5 presents the academic performance of the out of 23 individuals. The majority (59.52%) achieved a “Passing” level of academic performance. A smaller portion (13.39%) performed at the “Good” level, and 26.09% are at the “Very Good” level. The mean score is 88.27, with a standard deviation of 2.88, described as “Passing”, indicating that most scores in this group are close to the average. The overall qualitative description of the academic performance is “Passing.”

The data suggests that the group has a generally high academic standing, with over half of the individuals falling in the “Passing” category. The absence of any individuals in the “Excellent” category could imply a ceiling effect, perhaps due to challenging assessment standards, or that while students perform well, there may be barriers preventing them from excelling further. The relatively low standard deviation within the “Passing” category suggests consistency in performance among those students. Efforts could be focused on helping students bridge the gap from “Passing” to “Very Good” through enhanced instruction, enrichment programs, or personalized academic support. This data may inform educators or administrators about the effectiveness of the current teaching approaches and highlight potential areas for pedagogical refinement.

This result showed that graduates typically score higher on a comprehensive exam if they received higher academic marks in their general and professional education courses. The findings

demonstrated that graduates' academic achievement, as measured by their GWA in professional and general education, is a strong indicator of how well they will score on comprehensive exams. "The level of knowledge a person has gained is reflected in their performance on a given examination, and academic achievement plays a significant role in shaping exam results.

The findings from the CLE-focused study of Dagdagui and Mang-usan (2022) revealed that the academic performance of BS Criminology graduates was strong across the board. On the CLE, the graduates had a higher percentage of passers than non-passers. Most examinees passed all components of the CLE but struggled in the specialization subjects. Academic performance, strongly linked to CLE performance, supports the general conclusion that academic performance is a strong predictor of board examination success, and this extends to Criminology students taking the CLE, emphasizing that strong academic performance increases the likelihood of passing licensure exams.

Section 2. The Licensure Exam Performance of Criminology Graduates

Table 6

The Licensure Exam Performance of Criminology Graduates

Division	Mean	SD
Criminal Law and Jurisprudence	79.87	5.74
Law Enforcement Administration	79.87	16.06
Crime Detection and Investigation	78.87	4.63
Forensic/Criminalistics	79.61	3.51
Correctional Administration	85.04	4.46
Sociology of Crime and Ethics	80.09	6.30
AVERAGE RATING	80.76	3.90

Table 6 presents the performance of criminology students in the Criminology Licensure Examination from 2022 to 2024, showcasing their mean scores and standard deviations across various core subject areas. These subjects are critical components of the licensure exam and reflect students' preparedness to enter the field of law enforcement and criminal justice.

The licensure exam performance of criminology students, as detailed in the table, reveals a generally satisfactory academic achievement across the major subject areas. The highest performance was noted in Correctional Administration (CORRAD) with a mean score of 85.04 ($s=4.46$), suggesting students have strong competencies in legal knowledge and its applications. Meanwhile, the lowest mean score was recorded in CDI at 78.87 ($s=4.63$), which may indicate challenges in analytical and investigative aspects of criminology. CLJ and LEA both had mean scores of 79.87, but LEA had a higher standard deviation (16.06), pointing to inconsistent performance among students in that area. FS scored 79.61 ($s=3.51$), and CRIM received 80.09 ($s=6.30$), both showing moderate and relatively consistent performance. The overall average rating across all subjects was 80.76 ($s=3.90$), reflecting a generally acceptable level of knowledge, exceeding the passing threshold, though indicating variability in subject mastery.

The table implies that while criminology students are generally performing above the passing mark in the licensure examination, there are notable differences in their competence across subject areas. The strong performance in CORRAD suggests that legal education is a well-developed component of the criminology curriculum, possibly due to the emphasis placed on legal theory and jurisprudence in classroom instruction and review programs. However, the comparatively lower performance in CDI and high variability in LEA indicate that students may be struggling with practical

and operational aspects of criminology, such as investigative techniques and law enforcement strategies.

Barreda (2022) found a correlation between criminology graduates' performance on their licensure exam and their academic achievement. Based on her research, she talked about how students who passed their licensure exam performed better academically during their school years than those who did not. Academic performance is linked to good study habits, as demonstrated by other studies cited, and this study further demonstrates the importance of academic performance to graduates' chances of passing their licensure exam. This means that having good review habits will increase one's chances of passing the CLE.

Several local studies provide insights into factors influencing criminology students' performance in the CLE. Villarmia (2017) found that while theoretical subjects like Criminal Law were well-covered, practical fields needed more attention, prompting a call for stronger review programs. Parungao (2020) identified academic performance in core subjects as a significant predictor of board exam success, with weak preparation in investigative areas linked to lower scores. Similarly, Delos Santos and Castillo (2019) revealed that students excelled in legal and theoretical topics but underperformed in forensic and investigative areas, recommending enhanced training and simulation activities to address these gaps.

Individuals aspiring to work in the field of criminology or obtain licensure as criminologists are required to pass the CLE, which serves as evidence of their proficiency in essential subject areas. This examination reflects a criminologist's commitment to maintaining professional standards and ensures their ability to contribute meaningfully to the disciplines of criminal justice and criminology (Asuncion, 2019).

Section 3. Relationship between the profile variables (Emotional Quotient and Academic Performance) and the Criminology Licensure Examination

Table 7

Relationship between the profile variables (Emotional Quotient and Academic Performance) and the Criminology Licensure Examination

		CLJ	LEA	CDI	FS	CORRAD	CRIM	AVERAGE RATING
INTRA-PERSONAL	Correlation Coefficient	-0.394	-0.086	-0.260	-.475*	-.549**	-0.393	-.415*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.063	0.696	0.230	0.022	0.007	0.063	0.049
	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
INTER-PERSONAL	Correlation Coefficient	0.041	0.059	0.191	-0.133	-0.003	-0.262	-0.068
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.853	0.789	0.384	0.545	0.988	0.227	0.758
	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
STRESS MANAGEMENT	Correlation Coefficient	-0.112	0.131	0.010	-0.291	-0.350	-0.327	-0.200
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.610	0.553	0.962	0.178	0.102	0.127	0.360
	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
ADAPTABILITY	Correlation Coefficient	-0.052	-0.039	0.153	-0.045	-0.056	-0.204	-0.116
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.815	0.861	0.486	0.840	0.800	0.352	0.598
	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23

GENERAL MOOD	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
	Correlation Coefficient	-0.126	-0.084	-0.008	-0.080	0.066	-0.157	-0.120
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.568	0.704	0.971	0.717	0.765	0.473	0.587
TOTAL EQ	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
	Correlation Coefficient	-0.126	-0.043	0.070	-0.247	-0.144	-0.305	-0.199
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.566	0.847	0.751	0.256	0.511	0.156	0.363
POSITIVE IMPRESSION	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
	Correlation Coefficient	-0.228	-0.171	-0.258	-0.298	-0.185	-0.157	-0.284
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.296	0.435	0.235	0.167	0.398	0.475	0.189
GWA	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
	Correlation Coefficient	.611**	.565**	.564**	.467*	.427*	.466*	.621**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	0.005	0.005	0.025	0.042	0.025	0.002
	N	23	23	23	23	23	23	23

Table 7 reveals a statistically significant negative correlation between the "Intrapersonal" EQ dimension and performance in Forensic Science ($r = -0.475$, $p = 0.022$). This indicates that higher scores in Intrapersonal skills, as measured by the instrument used, are associated with lower scores in the Forensic Science examination. Even stronger negative correlations are observed with Correctional Administration ($r = -0.549$, $p = 0.007$) and Criminal Sociology ($r = -0.393$, $p = 0.063$). The majority of other EQ dimensions, including "Interpersonal" (r ranging from 0.041 to -0.003), "Stress Management" (r ranging from -0.112 to -0.350), "Adaptability" (r ranging from -0.052 to -0.056), "General Mood" (r ranging from -0.126 to -0.157), "Total EQ" (r ranging from -0.126 to -0.199), and "Positive Impression" (r ranging from -0.228 to -0.185), generally show no statistically significant correlations with any of the licensure examination divisions.

On the other hand, results demonstrated consistently strong and statistically significant positive correlations between General Weighted Average (GWA) and performance across all six divisions of the CLE, as well as the overall "Average Rating." The correlations range from $r = 0.427$ for Correctional Administration ($p=0.042$) to $r = 0.611$ for Criminal Jurisprudence ($p=0.002$).

Importantly, the GWA, representing overall academic performance prior to the licensure exam, demonstrates strong positive correlations with all CLE subjects, with correlation coefficients ranging from $\rho = 0.427$ to $\rho = 0.621$ ($p < 0.05$). This profile characteristic is still the best predictor of academic performance and can be quantified using the GWA on an ordinal scale. Depending on their GWA, students are frequently classified as high, average, or poor achievers (Magpily & Mercado, 2014). This suggests that students with higher academic achievements tend to perform better in the licensure examination, highlighting the importance of prior academic success as a predictor of licensure exam outcomes. According to Bañez and Pardo (2016), students who achieved higher grades in general education subjects tended to perform better on the licensure examination.

The observed negative correlations between Intrapersonal EQ and certain CLE subjects may imply that aspects such as heightened self-awareness or emotional sensitivity could potentially interfere with tasks requiring analytical thinking or decision-making, which are essential in criminology-related subjects. This finding underscores the complexity of emotional quotient and its nuanced impact on academic performance.

In the Philippine context, various studies highlight the significance of EQ and academic performance in educational success. Bance and Acopio (2016) found strong positive correlations between EQ dimensions and academic achievement among university students. Barreda (2022) emphasized that higher academic performance among criminology graduates positively impacts their Criminology Licensure Examination.

Section 4. Recommendations that can be advanced based on the findings of the study

In a recent dissemination initiative focused on the interplay between academic performance and emotional quotient (EQ), a comprehensive information campaign was conducted. This campaign aimed to highlight the significance of emotional quotient in academic settings and was tailored for key stakeholders, including Dr. Felipe V. Nantes Jr., the Dean of School of Teachers Education and Humanities, Mrs. Jeanette D. Manuel, the Department Head of Criminal Justice Education, and Mr. Samuel B. Damayon, the Dean of Student Affairs and Services (DSAS).

A professionally designed brochure served as the primary material for this campaign. It was structured to be both informative and engaging, ensuring clarity and retention of key messages. Summary of research findings indicating a positive correlation between high EQ and improved academic outcomes. Discussion on how EQ contributes to better stress management, enhanced communication skills, and increased motivation, all of which support academic success. To ensure the effective distribution and impact of the brochure, the dissemination plan was physical copies of the brochure were distributed to the offices of the Dean of STEH, Department Head of CJED, and the DSAS. For documentation and future reference, the brochure has been appended to the final report of the dissemination initiative.

This inclusion ensures that the material remains accessible for ongoing and future efforts to promote emotional quotient within the academic community. This information campaign underscores the institution's commitment to fostering environments where emotional quotient is recognized as a cornerstone of academic and personal development. Appendix A contains supplementary materials relevant to this section.

Conclusion. The researchers determined the relationship between academic performance and emotional quotient (EQ), and the Criminology Licensure Examination (CLE). Based on the findings, the following conclusions were generated:

1. The study's findings indicated that respondents' profiles specifically their EQ and academic performance are key in identifying the factors that may affect their outcomes in the Criminology Licensure Examination.
2. The performance of criminology students in the licensure examination from 2022 to 2024, particularly in the various subject areas, plays a vital role in the licensure process.
3. This study conducted a correlation analysis to investigate the relationship between different dimensions of EQ and the performance of criminology students in the CLE. It closely examined how key components of EQ, such as self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills, relate to student outcomes in the CLE.
4. Through a well-designed brochure that was both educational and captivating, the dissemination drives effectively presented the main research findings. Physical copies were carefully distributed to the Office of the DSAS, the Dean of STEH, and the Department Head of

CJED to guarantee that the information reached important institutional officials who have the power to influence student support services and educational practices.

Recommendation. Based on the findings of the study presented, the following recommendations can be advanced to improve both the academic and emotional preparedness of criminology students, particularly in relation to their performance in the Criminology Licensure Examination (CLE):

Criminology programs should integrate comprehensive EQ development initiatives into their academic curriculum. These may include structured workshops, seminars, and experiential learning designed to strengthen students' self-awareness, emotional regulation, stress management, empathy, and interpersonal communication.

Higher education institutions should establish an ongoing and systematic review process for criminology curricula and licensure exam preparation programs to ensure alignment with the competencies assessed in the CLE.

It is recommended that more empirical studies be conducted to identify which specific components of emotional quotient most strongly predict success in the CLE. Key dimensions such as self-regulation, motivation, social competence, and emotional awareness should be individually examined to determine their impact on academic performance and licensure outcomes.

To build upon the success of the initial dissemination effort and ensure the long-term impact of the campaign, it is recommended that the dissemination strategy be expanded through expanding the dissemination strategy by creating supplementary materials like posters, infographics, or brief video presentations based on the brochure to appeal to various learning styles and increase visibility throughout campus.

References

- Asuncion, R. L. (2019). Hitches encountered by criminology graduates of Isabela State University in the Criminologists Licensure Examination: A basis for proposed program enhancement. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 8(10), 323–363. <https://shorturl.at/rDN15>
- Badua, J. (2020). *Assessment of the CCJE licensure performance: Basis in enhancing instruction and review programs*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/347354237>
- Bance, L. O., & Acopio, J. R. B. (2016). Exploring emotional intelligence and academic performance of Filipino university academic achievers. *International Journal of Psychological Studies*, 8(3), 164–174. <https://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ijps/article/view/62045>
- Bañez, S. E., & Pardo, C. (2016). Licensure examination performance of BSEd-Biological and Physical Science graduates in a state university in Northern Philippines. *Journal of Educational and Human Resource Development*, 4, 119–132. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/389990897_Academic_Performance_and_Predictors_of_Licensure_Examination_for_Teachers_of_Bachelor_of_Elementary_Education_CORRESPONDING_AUTHOR

- Barreda, M. B. (2022). Academic performance of criminology graduates and its impact on the licensure examination for criminologists. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 7(5). <https://zenodo.org/records/6614390>
- Dagdagui, R. T., & Mang-usan, K. J. B. (2022). Correlates of licensure examination and college academic performance of teacher education graduates. *UP Los Baños Journal*, 20(2), 8. <https://www.ukdr.uplb.edu.ph/uplb-journal/vol20/iss2/8/>
- Delos Santos, M. J., & Castillo, R. (2019). Assessment of criminology students' competencies through mock board exams. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(4), 112–120.
- MacCann, C., Jiang, Y., Brown, L. E., Double, K. S., Bucich, M., & Minbashian, A. (2020). Emotional intelligence predicts academic performance: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 146(2), 150–186. <https://psycnet.apa.org/buy/2019-74947-001>
- Magpily, M. P., & Mercado, J. (2014). *ATINER's Conference Paper Series EDU2014-1123*. <http://www.atiner.gr/papers/EDU2014-1123.pdf>
- Parungao, R. (2020). Academic performance as predictor of board examination success among criminology graduates. *Philippine Journal of Criminology*, 12(2), 45–58. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=15325>
- Sánchez-Álvarez, N., Berrios Martos, M. P., & Extremera, N. (2020). A meta-analysis of the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance in secondary education: A multi-stream comparison. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1517. <https://philpapers.org/rec/SNCAMO>
- Villarmia, J. C. (2017). *Perception of graduates towards their preparation for the Criminology Licensure Examination*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=13830>